

Real-Time Alert Mechanisms in an IoT-Enabled Smart Medication Monitoring System Using a Pill Box and Liquid Bottle.

Wijesinghe A.S.N, Rathnayake R.M.K.N, Yapa A.I

¹Faculty of Information Technology, Horizon Campus, Malabe, Sri Lanka.

Abstract

Non-adherence to medicine is a significant health care issue, especially among geriatric and chronic care patients, and its prevalence rates are estimated at 40-50. This results in much worse health care and health expenditure. Current options, including simple pillboxes, do not include real-time monitoring features, and intelligent dispensers available in the market do not necessarily support liquid drugs and multi-user features. To fill in these gaps, this paper has suggested a new cost-effective hybrid platform based on Arduino/Raspberry Pi microcontrollers. The system consists of the integration of a smart pillbox and a liquid dispenser using an ultrasonic flow sensor to measure the liquid accurately. It allows real-time tracking through cloud connectivity and sends multi-modal notifications (LED, SMS, and wearable alerts) to remind the user. The strategy is expected to be far better than traditional tactics, relying on past studies that show an increase in adherence of more than 20% with the use of similar IoT tools. The suggested system will be scalable, patient-centered, and affordable, and it will be a platform on which additional adherence and access optimization tools can be added, such as AI-driven reminders, blockchain security, and voice control.

Keywords: *Visuals Alerts (LED), Auditory Alerts (Buzzers), Tactile Alerts (Wearable Vibrations), SMS, App Notifications.*